

Comparison of strategies for automatic video-based detection of piling behaviour in laying hens

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ABSTRACT

This study addresses piling behaviour in laying hens, a concern for producers due to welfare issues. Piling is commonly defined as the intense aggregation of birds into dense clusters, typically occurring in large group-housing systems. This behaviour can lead to severe welfare issues including suffocation for the affected birds, particularly those at the bottom of the pile. This is a preliminary study, using video data from 4 commercial Swiss layer flocks. The long-term goal of our research is to develop a machine learning-based method to automatically detect piling behaviour using a two-step approach: first, a pre-trained convolutional neural network model (VGG-16) is used to extract features from the video data. Second, a secondary model, trained specifically to detect piling, is applied to the extracted features. The specific aim of this preliminary study is to determine which secondary modelling strategy is best suited for the accurate and efficient detection of piling behaviour. Three secondary methods are explored, namely fully connected artificial neural networks (FC-ANN), long-short term memory (LSTM) networks, and convolutional neural networks (CNN).

1. Introduction

Piling is an undesired behaviour in flocks of laying hens, where individuals aggregate in dense clusters [1–3]. Winter et al. [3] defines piling behaviour as “three or more mostly immobile (maximal movement duration < 5 s) hens standing in closest possible proximity (overlapping of body outlines) with most hens facing in the same direction”. The behaviour occurs in loose group-housing systems and can result in birds suffocating at the bottom of the pile [3], and a study by Armstong et al. [2] suggests that piling might negatively affect egg production. Piling is a major concern for egg producers because of its welfare implications [4]. Early detection of piling behaviour is crucial for mitigating this welfare issue, but manual monitoring of large flocks is time-consuming. This is where automatic detection systems can play a pivotal role in improving animal health and welfare. Continuous monitoring through automatic systems can help identify patterns and triggers of piling behaviour, related to e.g. breed or barn systems, enabling farmers to implement proactive management strategies to prevent future occurrences.

In recent years, several studies have described how the behaviour of farmed animals can be automatically classified from video data by utilizing pre-trained convolutional neural networks (CNNs). The use of pre-trained models leverages the power of transfer learning, allowing the model to benefit from features learned on large datasets including images from 1000 different categories without requiring an equally large dataset for the specific task at hand. This is particularly valuable in agricultural settings, where obtaining large annotated datasets can be challenging and time-consuming. Moreover, pre-trained models often demonstrate robust performance across a range of visual tasks, making them well-suited for adapting to the complexities of animal behaviour detection.

For example, Quach et al. [5] implemented VGGNet [6] and ResNet [7], models pre-trained on the ImageNet data set [8], to identify chickens with various common diseases against healthy individuals. Chen et al. [9] (2020) used VGG-16 [6] combined with a long-short term memory (LSTM) network to detect aggressive episodes between pigs. Similarly, Hakansson & Jensen [10] (2023) used the same pre-trained

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VGG-16 model combined with an LSTM as well as a secondary convolutional neural network (CNN) for detecting tail biting in nursing piglets. The studies showed that utilizing a pre-trained model in combination with a secondary model trained for a specific task is suitable for the implementation of models for specific classification problems.

This is a preliminary study and is intended to inform our future strategy with respect to developing piling detection models. The specific aim of this study is to use the same pre-trained VGG-16 model as was used in the studies mentioned above and compare 3 different secondary models for automatic detection of piling behaviour in group-housed laying hens based on video data recorded at 4 commercial Swiss flocks. In addition to LSTM and CNN as secondary models, we will also use fully connected artificial neural networks (FC-ANN). In the past, FC-ANNs have been used for multiple tasks related to animal monitoring, such as early prediction of pen fouling behaviour in fattening pigs [11] and mastitis detection in dairy cows [12]. FC-ANNs have the advantage, compared to CNN and LSTM, of being simple, and are thus less computationally demanding both at training and at inference. Being less computationally demanding is an advantage when deploying the model in practice, where it will most likely need to run on local hardware in the barns. Lower computational requirements can lead to more cost-effective implementation, making the technology more accessible to a wider range of farmers. However, FC-ANNs have the disadvantage of not being well suited for sequential data, unlike LSTM and CNN.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Data source

For this study, video data collected in the winter garden of 4 farms with white birds were used. The details of the farms and the camera specifications have been described previously by Winter et al. (Winter et al., 2021, Table 1 Flocks 5, 7, 11, and 12). Data from additional farms were available, but for the purposes of this preliminary study, only data from the winter gardens of these four flocks with only white birds have been utilized, as the picture qualities were found to be best in these videos; as this is a preliminary study, we wanted to make sure the idea worked on a relatively easy scenario before advancing to more difficult, although more relevant, scenarios.

Fig. 1 shows two images for each of the included cameras i.e., one image without piling (top row) and one image with piling (bottom row). For this study, data from the first 4 cameras (3 flocks) seen in Fig. 1 were used as a training set, while data from the right-most flock seen in Fig. 1 was used as a test set. This stratification by flock was done to avoid data leakage between the training and the test set, i.e. to make sure the training set and the test set were mutually independent. The last flock was chosen for the test set because it contained the largest number of unique piling and non-piling events.

The video data were provided with the annotations regarding the presence or absence of piling defined and used by Winter et al. [3]. The intra-observer reliability for the piling labels was evaluated in a previous study and found to be $> 94\%$ [3].

During the day, the cameras recorded RGB images, while they recorded IR images at night. By converting both image types to greyscale, a single model could be made and used for all lighting conditions,

Table 1

Overview of the basic architecture used for the fully connected neural networks. $N_{PC} = 2^n$ principal components, where $n \in [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9]$.

Layer	Size	Activation function
Input	N_{PC}	
Batch normalization	N_{PC}	
Dropout	40%	
Fully connected	$(2/3) \cdot N_{PC}$	ReLU
Batch normalization	$(2/3) \cdot N_{PC}$	
Fully connected	2	Softmax

rather than needing separate models for day and night-time. It is expected that this strategy will also be useful in future studies to mitigate the issues of poor lighting conditions inside the layer sheds.

2.2. Data encoding and pre-processing

From the video sequences, still-frames were extracted at 1 second intervals using the free open-source tool *FFmpeg* [13], and the images were rescaled to 224×224 pixels.

All subsequent data encoding and pre-processing was done in R (Version 3.6.1).

The frames from all video data (i.e. both training and test set) were encoded into numerical vector representations using the publicly available VGG-16 model [14], pre-trained on the ImageNet data set [8]. This was done using the *Keras* package (Version 2.9.0) for R. The VGG-16 model was truncated at its flattening layer (i.e., the fully-connected layers and the Softmax output layer were removed), meaning that the input image was encoded into a vector with 25,088 features. The variance of all features from the training set was calculated. Any features which had a variance of 0 in the training set were removed from both the training set and the test set.

Principle component analysis (PCA) was then performed using the *prcomp* function in R to identify the principal components of the encoded vectors on the training set. The principal component transformations were learned from the training set and subsequently applied to both the training and the test set.

2.3. Secondary model definitions

The principal components of the encoded images were used as inputs for the secondary models, which were trained to detect the absence or presence of piling. Three different types of neural networks were tested for the secondary models, namely FC-ANN, LSTM, and CNN. While the FC-ANN can only utilize a single encoded still-image at a time as input data, the two other architectures are able to utilize sequences of encoded images as input data.

For all the secondary models, the output was a binary classification of piling behaviour (0/1 = no/yes).

All secondary models were trained and tested in R (Version 3.6.1), using the *Keras* package (Version 2.9.0).

2.3.1. Fully connected artificial neural network

A series of FC-ANNs was trained to take the first N_{PC} principal components (with $N_{PC} = 2^n$ principal components, where $n \in [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9]$) as input and produce a binary piling classification as its output.

The architecture of the FC-ANN comprises an input layer with N_{PC} input nodes representing the first N_{PC} principal components, followed by batch normalization, followed by a dropout layer with a 40% dropout rate (only used during training). This is followed by a fully connected hidden layer with $(2/3) \cdot N_{PC}$ nodes utilizing ReLU activation, followed by another batch normalization layer. The output layer consists of a fully connected layer with 2 nodes employing the Softmax activation function. Table 1 provides an overview of the architecture.

The value of N_{PC} was varied to identify the optimal value. Only one hidden layer was used in the FC-ANN to keep it as simple as possible, as one hidden layer is known to be sufficient for most classification problems [15].

2.3.2. Long-short term memory

For the LSTM models, we used a sequence-to-class architecture, where sequences of N_{obs} image-representations (corresponding to N_{obs} frames, as we use one frame per second) are mapped to the binary piling classification. The architecture of the LSTM comprises an input layer for $N_{obs} \times N_{PC}$ inputs, followed by batch normalization, an LSTM layer, a dropout layer with a 25% dropout rate, and a Softmax output layer with

Fig. 1. Image examples of birds distributed normally (top) and piling (bottom) in the winter gardens of the five different cameras in four different flocks with white birds. The red rectangles indicate the locations of the piling events. Each column represents videos collected in different flocks, except the second and the third column which represent two cameras in the same flock. The flocks in columns 1 through 4 were used as a training set, while data from the flock seen in the fifth column was used as the test set.

Table 2

Overview of the basic architecture used for the long short-term memory networks. $N_{PC} = 2^n$ principal components, where $n \in [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9]$. $N_{obs} = 2^n$ is the sequence length, where $n \in [2, 3, 4, 5]$.

Layer	Size	Activation function
Input	$N_{obs} \times N_{PC}$	
LSTM	$(2/3) \cdot (N_{obs}/4) \cdot (N_{PC}/4) \cdot 16$	ReLU
Dropout	25%	
Fully connected	2	Softmax

2 nodes. [Table 2](#) provides an overview of the architecture.

The value of N_{PC} was varied to identify the optimal value, with $N_{PC} = 2^n$ principal components, where $n \in [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9]$. Similarly, the value of N_{obs} was varied to identify the optimal value, with $N_{obs} = 2^n$ being the sequence length, where $n \in [2, 3, 4, 5]$. Only a single LSTM layer was used in this study, based on experiences from a previous study on detecting tail biting behaviour in piglets, which showed that adding additional LSTM layers did not improve the performance [10].

Table 3

Overview of the basic architecture used for the convolutional neural networks. $N_{PC} = 2^n$ principal components, where $n \in [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9]$. $N_{obs} = 2^n$ is the sequence length, where $n \in [2, 3, 4, 5]$.

Layer	Size	No. of kernels	Kernel size	Activation function
Input	$N_{obs} \times N_{PC} \times 1$			
Convolution	$N_{obs} \times N_{PC} \times 1$	8	3×3	ReLU
Batch normalization	$N_{obs} \times N_{PC} \times 8$			
Dropout	25%			
Convolution	$N_{obs} \times N_{PC} \times 8$	8	3×3	ReLU
Batch normalization	$N_{obs} \times N_{PC} \times 8$			
Max pooling	2×2			
Dropout	25%			
Convolution	$(N_{obs}/2) \times (N_{PC}/2) \times 8$	16	3×3	ReLU
Batch normalization	$(N_{obs}/2) \times (N_{PC}/2) \times 16$			
Dropout	25%			
Convolution	$(N_{obs}/2) \times (N_{PC}/2) \times 16$	16	3×3	ReLU
Batch normalization	$(N_{obs}/2) \times (N_{PC}/2) \times 16$			
Max pooling	2×2			
Dropout	25%			
Flattening	$(N_{obs}/4) \cdot (N_{PC}/4) \cdot 16$			
Fully connected	$(2/3) \cdot (N_{obs}/4) \cdot (N_{PC}/4) \cdot 16$			ReLU
Batch normalization	$(2/3) \cdot (N_{obs}/4) \cdot (N_{PC}/4) \cdot 16$			
Dropout	50%			
Fully connected	2			Softmax

2.3.3. Convolutional neural network

We implemented a series of CNNs as an alternative method for handling sequences of encoded images. The basic architecture described below was based on the architecture used in a previous study [16] where it had proven successful for counting the number of pigs in a given image. Here, the principal components of the encoded images were combined into a $N_{obs} \times N_{PC}$ matrix and used as input for the CNNs.

The architecture of the CNN comprises an input layer with dimensions $N_{obs} \times N_{PC}$ followed by a convolutional layer employing 8 kernels of size 3×3 with ReLU activation, followed by batch normalization. A dropout layer with a rate of 25% is then applied. This is followed by another convolutional layer with identical parameters as the previous one, followed by batch normalization, max pooling of size 2×2 , and another dropout layer with a 25% rate. Subsequently, two more pairs of convolutional layers with 16 kernels each are applied, each followed by batch normalization, max pooling, and dropout with the same rate. After flattening the output, a fully connected layer with N_{hidden} nodes and ReLU activation, batch normalization, and a dropout rate of 50% is utilized. Finally, a fully connected output layer with 2

nodes and Softmax activation function concludes the network architecture.

The length of the flattening layer, $N_{flatten}$, could be calculated as $(N_{obs}/4) \cdot (N_{PC}/3) \cdot 16$. The value of N_{hidden} was then defined as $(2/3) \cdot N_{flatten}$. Table 3 shows an overview of the basic CNN architecture.

The value of N_{PC} was varied to identify the optimal value, with $N_{PC} = 2^n$ principal components, where $n \in [2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9]$. Similarly, the value of N_{obs} was varied to identify the optimal value, with $N_{obs} = 2^n$ being the sequence length, i.e. the number of frames included in the input, where $n \in [2, 3, 4, 5]$.

2.4. Training and early stopping

All models were trained using a the *adam* optimizer with the categorical cross-entropy loss function. A batch size of 16 was used.

Early stopping with a patience of 10 was used. This means that after each training epoch, the model was applied to the test set, and training stopped when the loss on the test set had failed to decrease for 10 consecutive epochs. At this point, the version of the model with the lowest loss on the test set was restored and returned. Per-event aggregation (see below) was not applied to the predictions while training with early stopping.

2.5. Performance evaluation

After training, the secondary models were applied to the encoded and PCA-transformed test data. The performances were assessed on a per-event basis, i.e. based on the predictions for each unique piling event or non-piling event, as opposed to being based on the predictions for each frame or input sequence. This allows for direct comparison between the three different approaches. This was done by aggregating the output of each of the secondary models to a simple mean value per unique coherent piling event or non-piling event. Receiver operating characteristics (ROC) curves were then made by testing all thresholds between 0 and 1 by steps of 0.01 for a positive prediction. The models were then assessed based on the area under the ROC curve (AUC) and the highest major mean accuracy (MMA, defined as the mean of sensitivity and specificity) achieved for any threshold value.

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive statistics

Table 4 shows the number of unique coherent piling and non-piling events, as well as the total number of images extracted from each camera at 1 frame per second in each of the included flocks, along with summary statistics of the duration of the recorded piling and non-piling events, and whether the frames were used as part of the training set or test set.

3.2. Performance

The FC-ANN achieved its highest MMA of 76 % when using 32 principal components. The LSTM achieved its highest MMA of 86 %

when using 32 principal components and a sequence length of 16 frames. The CNN reached its highest MMA of 90 % when using 256 principal components and a sequence length of 16 frames. Fig. 2 summarizes the performances of the best versions of the three types of models in terms of ROC curves (top row) confusion matrices of the predictions (middle row) and the distribution of the estimated probability for piling given the ground truth (bottom row).

4. Discussion

It is seen from Fig. 2 that the AUC of the best LSTM and the best CNN are nearly identical, while the AUC of the best FC-ANN is considerably lower than for the two other approaches. It is further seen that the best LSTM has a better sensitivity (confusion matrix, lower right corner) than the best CNN, while the specificity (confusion matrix, upper right corner) is higher for best CNN compared to the best LSTM. The best FC-ANN has the lowest sensitivity of three approaches.

Lastly, it is seen from the prediction distributions (bottom row) that both the best LSTM and the best CNN achieve good separation, while the separation is comparatively poor for the best FC-ANN. Furthermore, it is seen that the best LSTM has an optimal threshold very close the naïve threshold of 50 %, while the best FC-ANN and especially the best CNN have optimal thresholds far below 50 %.

From these results it becomes clear that the two approaches which can consider sequences of frames (i.e., LSTM and CNN) outperform the method which can only consider one frame at a time (i.e. FC-ANN). While the best CNN slightly outperformed the best LSTM in terms of MMA and AUC, the best LSTM has the advantage of having an optimal threshold for positive prediction close to the naïve threshold of 50 %, and the advantage of requiring fewer principal components in its input (32 compared to 256). This is an advantage in terms of reducing the required computing power when utilizing the model in a practical setting.

5. Limitations

Piling behaviour was defined and labelled by a single observer [3], potentially introducing subjectivity in determining exactly when the behaviour changes from non-piling to piling and vice versa. This will lead to some uncertainty about which frames near the beginning and end of a piling event should be included in the piling event, and which frames should be included in the surrounding non-piling events. Even so, since the models were evaluated on their performance on entire coherent events of piling and non-piling, and not on a per-frame basis, we consider this to be less of an issue.

The developed models were based only on data from white birds in winter gardens. This means that the models will likely have a limited ability to generalize to other and more relevant settings, such as brown birds inside the layer barn. Future research should further develop the models with a focus on detecting piling under different scenarios.

Only data from Swiss farms were included, and so the ability of the models to generalize to farms in different countries may be limited. Further studies would benefit from including data from a variety of

Table 4

Descriptive statistics of the five cameras from the four flocks, which were included in this study.

Flock/Camera	Used for	No. of piling events	No. of non-piling events	No. of images	Event duration, seconds					
					Min.	1st Qu.	Median	Mean	3rd Qu.	Max.
1	Training set	3	3	5482	339	424	561	914	1521	1802
2.A		18	8	13,648	96	247	548	525	875	902
2.B		2	3	2861	246	357	456	572	901	901
3		13	7	12,598	111	306	420	630	942	1802
4	Test set	21	11	17,186	18	226	422	537	901	902

Fig. 2. Left column: FC-ANN. Middle column: LSTM. Right column: CNN. Top row: ROC curves for the best architectures of each of the three types of secondary models, along with the AUC of each curve. The dashed lines represent the sensitivities and 1-specificities achieved with the threshold, which results in the best MMA for the given model. Middle row: Confusion matrices of the best architecture of each of the three types of secondary models. Bottom row: Class separation capabilities of the best architecture of each of the three types of secondary models, as represented by distributions of model output given the ground truth state. The blue dashed lines show the threshold which results in the highest MMA, while the red dashed lines represent a naïve threshold of 50 % probability for piling. The height of the bars represents the median estimated probability for piling for each class, while the error bars represent the first and third quartile of the estimated probability for piling per class.

different countries with different housing and management conditions.

Only one pre-trained model (VGG16) was used for initial video frame encoding, potentially overlooking benefits of other pre-trained architectures. Future research should aim to address these limitations to develop more robust and widely applicable piling detection systems.

6. Conclusion

The LSTM and CNN both outperformed the FC-ANN as secondary models for detecting piling behaviour in laying hens from features extracted via the pre-trained VGG-16 model. Although the CNN outperformed the LSTM slightly in terms of AUC and MMA, it required more

principal components (and thus more computing power) to do so, and the optimal classification threshold was far below the naïve threshold of 50 %, unlike the case of LSTM.

We therefore consider the LSTM to be the best of the three tested approaches.

Ethical note

This study was entirely based on data collected in a previous study [3], and so no new ethical approval was needed to conduct this study. The authors of the previous study had obtained the ethical approval to conduct their study from the Veterinary Office of the Canton of Bern,

Switzerland (approval number BE97/17), and the animals were treated in compliance with the Swiss regulations regarding the treatment of animals involved in research.

Ethics statement

This research used pre-existing data collected for a previous study with a different aim than this study. The ethical approval to conduct the previous study was obtained from the Veterinary Office of the Canton of Bern, Switzerland (approval number BE97/17). The animals were treated in compliance with the Swiss regulations regarding the treatment of animals involved in research.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Dan Børge Jensen: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Michael Toscano:** Writing – review & editing. **Esther van der Heide:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Matias Grønvig:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Franziska Hakansson:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Software, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

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